

iPhone SE (2022) 64GB setup documentation

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Basic steps (pictures on the next slide)

- Pressing home button to choose language
 - Picked language: English
- Selecting country/region
 - Selected: Germany (already preselected)
- Choosing size and font of text
 - Default options retained
- Setup with other phone?
 - Opted not to
- Keyboard instructions
 - No customisation

Screenshots are not possible during the setup process, pictures taken with other phone

Select Your Country or Region

Germany >

More Countries and Regions

Afghanistan >

Åland Islands >

Albania >

Algeria >

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Written and Spoken Languages

The following languages are commonly used in your region. You can set up your iPhone to use these settings or customise them individually.

Preferred Languages

English
German

Keyboards

English (UK)
Deutsch (Deutschland)
Emoji

Continue

Customise Settings

Deutsch >

Français >

Nederlands >

Italiano >

Español >

Русский >

English >

No SIM

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Appearance

Choose the size of text and icons on iPhone.

Default

Medium

Large

Continue

No SIM

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Quick Start

✳ Looking for nearby devices...

Bring your current iPhone or iPad near this iPhone to sign in and set up.

If your other iPhone or iPad doesn't show options for setting up this iPhone, make sure it's running iOS 11 or later, and has Bluetooth turned on. You can also set up this iPhone manually.

[Set Up Without Another Device](#)

Choosing Wi-Fi network

- Picked eduroam and logged on with my student access
 - Trusting the certificate
- iPhone activation ongoing

Data & Privacy

- Picking „Continue“
- Set Up iPhone: Set up for myself

Setting up locking options

- Touch ID: set up later
- Creating iPhone passcode: 123456
 - Warning: Use anyway

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Create an iPhone Passcode

Create a passcode you will use to unlock this iPhone.

Passcode Options

1	2 ABC	3 DEF
4 GHI	5 JKL	6 MNO
7 PQRS	8 TUV	9 WXYZ
	0	⌫

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Create an iPhone

This Passcode Can Be Easily Guessed

Your passcode will be used to unlock this iPhone and to protect access to your data stored in iCloud.

[Use Anyway](#)

[Change Passcode](#)

Transferring Data and Apps

- Not transferring anything

Apple ID (documentation on following slides)

- No apple ID → Creating a free apple ID
 - DICE Apple ID
 - Name: DICE HHU
 - Date of birth: 10th April 2000
- Asked for E-Mail adress: getting an icloud E-Mail adress
 - dicephoneproject@icloud.com
- Apple ID Password: Registration10.11
- Verification phone number: my private phone number
 - Verification via text message

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Apple ID

Sign in with an email or phone number to use iCloud, the App Store and other Apple services.

Email or Phone Number

[Forgot password or don't have an Apple ID?](#)

Your Apple ID information is used to enable Apple services when you sign in, including iCloud Backup, which automatically backs up the data on your device in case you need to replace or restore it. Your device serial number may be used to check eligibility for service offers. [See how your data is managed...](#)

Continue

[Use Multiple Accounts](#)

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Apple ID

[Forgot Password or Apple ID](#) >

[Create a Free Apple ID](#) >

[Set Up Later in Settings](#) >

What is an Apple ID?

An Apple ID is the account you use to access everything Apple. You can sign in to all Apple services with a single Apple ID and password.

Get all your content on all your devices automatically, with iCloud.

Find the best selection of apps in the App Store.

Shop for music, movies, TV shows and more in the iTunes Store.

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Name and Date of Birth

DICE

HHU

Date of birth 10.04.00

[April 2000](#) v

January 1997

February 1998

March 1999

April 2000

May 2001

Continue

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Email Address

Email address

This will be your new Apple ID.

[Do not have an email address?](#)

Announcements

Receive Apple emails and communications including announcements, marketing, recommendations and updates about Apple products, services and software.

Continue

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Phone Number

Please enter a phone number that can be used to verify your identity via text message or phone call.

+49 (Germany) >

phone number

VERIFY USING:

Text message

Phone call

Messaging or data rates may apply.

Continue

Terms and conditions

- Agree to all
- Signing in

Additional settings

- Automatic updates: continue
- Location services: enabled
- Setting up mobile service: set up later in settings
- Screen time: set up later in settings
- Analytics: don't share
- Light or dark display: light

No SIM 11:44

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Analytics

Help Apple improve its products and services, including Siri and other intelligent features, by allowing analytics of usage and data from your iPhone and iCloud account. You can change your decision later in Settings.

All analysis is performed using privacy preserving techniques such as differential privacy and is not associated with you or your account.

[Learn More...](#)

Share with Apple

Don't Share

No SIM 11:44

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Light or Dark Display

Select a light or dark appearance and see how iPhone adjusts depending on which one you choose.

Light Dark Auto

Continue

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Screen Time

Get a weekly report with insights about your screen time and set time limits for apps you want to manage. You can also use Screen Time on children's devices and set up parental controls.

Continue

[Set Up Later in Settings](#)

No SIM 11:44

Welcome to iPhone

Get Started

Home screen and standard apps

notable preinstalled apps by apple:

- Facetime
- Apple tv
- Safari browser
(only browser preinstalled)
- Apple Maps
- Apple podcasts
- iTunes
- etc.

First time opening Safari

- Several search engines offered on starting page
 - Searching in the low search bar without picking one
- Standard search engine: Google
 - Accepting terms and conditions of google → accept all

Default cloud storage: iCloud

- Many apps are by standard connected to iCloud

First time opening app store

- Allowing app store to use location? → allow while using app
 - Interestingly, location is already shown before permission is given
- Some recommended apps but no other E-Mail programs or browsers

First time opening E-Mail

- Protect mail activity
- Allow notifications
- E-Mail is connected to apple ID

Downloading an app from outside the app store

- Trying to download Telegram messenger through chip.de
 - The usual download of Fortnite was not possible
 - Clicking download automatically for Telegram forwards you into the app store
 - „open in Safari“ also not possible
- Online search shows that apple apparently does not allow the installations of external apps
 - <https://www.wired.com/story/install-apps-outside-app-store-sideload/>

No SIM 12:17

CHIP

Jetzt Quereinstieg sichern

Bewirb dich jetzt und sichere dir deinen Einstieg zum 01.11. oder 01.04.

Deloitte [Jetzt Bewerben](#)

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Version 10.1.2 | Rang 4 / 318 bei CHIP in der Kategorie: Social Networks

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15K RATINGS **3.7** ★★★★★

AGE **17+** Years Old

CHART **No.2** Social Networking

Fast

Simple, reliable and synced across all your devices.

Power

No limits on the groups and bre...

Today Games Apps Arcade Search

Differences to setting up Samsung and Google phones

- No Google account needed to be created or to be signed in with which was obligatory when setting up Android and Google phones. However, an Apple ID must be set up, which is logically not required for the other operating systems.
 - Google services as well as their Privacy and Terms did not have to be accepted.
 - No Personalization settings
- Many pre-installed apps that are provided by Apple itself (Apple tv, Apple podcasts, Apple Maps, iTunes etc.). Also, iCloud is used as default cloud storage, and is connected to many other apps.

Differences to setting up Samsung and Google phones

- Default search engine: Google Search
 - Samsung: Google Search
 - Google: Google Search
- Default internet browser: Safari
 - Samsung: Samsung Internet (Google Chrome also available; Firefox, UC Browser, Microsoft Edge and Opera were at least suggested)
 - Google: Google Chrome (no other available; Firefox was suggested for download from Google Play)
- Default mail program: Apple Mail
 - Samsung: Gmail
 - Google: Gmail
- Default digital assistant: Siri
 - Samsung: Google Assistant
 - Google: Google Assistant